

*Performance of College of Education Graduates in the
Licensure Examination for Teachers: A Descriptive Study*

Chard Aye Reyes Alova, University of St. La Salle

Abstract

One of the College of Education's most important priorities is to maintain and advance the passing rate of its graduates in the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET). It is a manifestation of quality education offered by that Higher Education Institution (HEI), specifically a Teacher Education Institution (TEI). As a result, the goal of this study is to show a descriptive report of the results of the 2019 Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) of a certain public Higher Education Institution (HEI) in the Philippines. Results show that the LET performance is generally passing but still quite low (Mean=79.542, SD=5.566). The Math and English majors exhibit high performance in the General and Professional Education subjects compared to the other programs, and the Math majors attained the highest performance in the Major subject among the other programs.

Keywords: *Teacher Education, Higher Education, Licensure Examination for Teachers, Pre-Service Teacher Education, College of Education*

Introduction

One of the Philippine government's top priorities is high-quality education. Republic Act No. 7836, an act to enhance the supervision and regulation of the practice of teaching in the Philippines and administering a Licensure Examination for Teachers was enacted to ensure a

minimum degree of competence for teachers. To be eligible for a license to teach in elementary and secondary schools, all graduates of education courses must pass this exam (Philippine Teachers Professionalization Act of 1994).

All graduates of a teacher education degrees are required to take the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) to exercise his or her profession. Those who pass the board exam will gain not only honor and prestige, but you'll also have a competitive advantage over non-LET passers. As a result, Higher Education Institutions that offer teacher education programs bear the difficult but transcendent obligation of increasing the number of qualified teachers. The abundance of standards, norms, and determining factors for an institution's success reflects the public's concern for quality education. The achievement of a Higher Education Institution's graduates on the licensure examination is a prominent means of measuring its success (Pachejo and Allaga, 2014).

Methodology

Descriptive research design employing survey method was used in this study. Descriptive research design is a study designed to depict the participants in an accurate way. More simply put, descriptive research is all about describing people who take part in the study and it can be done using observational, case study, or survey (Kowalczyk, 2015).

The participants of the study were be the College of Education graduates of a particular public HEI in Negros Occidental, Philippines. The participants were first time takers of the Licensure Examination for Teachers last 2019, right after they graduated. They were enrolled in various College of Education degrees, such as, Bachelor in Elementary Education: major in General Education and Early Childhood Education, and Bachelor in Secondary Education: major in English, Filipino, Mathematics and Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health (MAPEH).

This study employed total enumeration method in gathering the data, that is, utilizing the entire population College of Education graduates (n=183) who specifically took the Licensure Examination last 2019. The LET performance of the graduates were gathered and provided by the participants as taken from the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC), the LET performance was further categorized into General Education, Professional Education, and Major Subject.

Levels	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
BSED FILIPINO	29	15.8 %	15.8 %
BSED ENGLISH	35	19.1 %	35.0 %
BEED ECE	26	14.2 %	49.2 %
BSED MAPEH	20	10.9 %	60.1 %
BSED MATH	28	15.3 %	75.4 %
BEED GENED	45	24.6 %	100.0 %

Table 1. Frequency Distribution of Participants categorized by College of Education degrees

Results and Discussion

The profile of the participants were analyzed using a Frequency Distribution which Table 1 shows, and the Bachelor in Elementary Education major in General Education has highest number of participants that is 45 (24.6%) and the Bachelor of Secondary Education major in MAPEH has the lowest number of participants that is 20 (10.9%).

Table 2 reveals all the descriptives which the paper intends to show. Here, we can see that in the General Education subject, the Math majors achieved the highest mean score (Mean=83.750, SD=4.567). Second to the highest were the English majors (Mean=82.771, SD=4.512). Third to the highest were the MAPEH majors (Mean=80.900, SD=4.327). The highest scorers are both found in the Math and English majors which is 91 out of 150 (60.67%) among all the takers in the subject category. The degree that landed the lowest mean score were the Early Childhood Education majors (Mean=77.885, SD=6.095). We can also find the lowest scorer in the Early Childhood Education majors which is 51 out of 150 (34.00%).

In the Professional Education Category, the degree that achieved the highest mean score were the English majors (Mean=80.486, SD=3.936), also recording the highest score of 89 out of 150 (59.33%) among all the takers of the subject category. Second to the highest were the Math majors (Mean=79.393, SD=2.859), and the third to the highest were the General Education majors (Mean=78.600, SD=4.520). While the Early Childhood Education majors earned the lowest mean score (Mean=74.423, SD=7.322), the lowest scorer is a Filipino major which is 45 out of 150 (30.00%) among all takers of the subject category.

In the Major Subject, the General Education majors and Early Childhood Education majors do not have major subjects in the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET), hence

	Degree	N	Mean	95% Confidence Interval		SD	Minimum	Maximum
				Lower	Upper			
ProfEd	BSED FILIPINO	29	77.172	74.768	79.577	6.607	45	82
	BSED ENGLISH	35	80.486	79.182	81.790	3.936	72	89
	BEED ECE	26	74.423	71.609	77.238	7.322	57	87
	BSED MAPEH	20	78.350	76.752	79.948	3.646	67	82
	BSED MATH	28	79.393	78.334	80.452	2.859	69	83
	BEED GENED	45	78.600	77.279	79.921	4.520	60	85
GenEd	BSED FILIPINO	29	80.000	78.230	81.770	4.862	65	88
	BSED ENGLISH	35	82.771	81.277	84.266	4.512	77	91
	BEED ECE	26	77.885	75.542	80.227	6.095	51	85
	BSED MAPEH	20	80.900	79.003	82.797	4.327	72	88
	BSED MATH	28	83.750	82.058	85.442	4.567	69	91
	BEED GENED	45	78.356	77.028	79.683	4.544	68	90
Major	BSED FILIPINO	29	80.138	77.778	82.498	6.485	54	87
	BSED ENGLISH	35	77.743	75.458	80.027	6.896	56	87
	BEED ECE	0	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
	BSED MAPEH	20	79.750	77.930	81.570	4.153	72	86
	BSED MATH	28	83.321	81.610	85.032	4.619	73	92
	BEED GENED	0	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

Table 2. Performance of College of Education in the Licensure Examination for Teachers subdivided into Degree and Exam

table 2 only shows the results for the Filipino, English, MAPEH, and Math majors. The Math majors achieved the highest mean score (Mean=83.321, SD=4.619), next from the highest were the Filipino majors (Mean=80.138, SD=6.485), third from the highest were the MAPEH majors (Mean=79.750, SD=4.153). The English majors received the lowest mean score (Mean=77.743, SD=6.896). The highest scorer of the major subject was from the Math majors who achieved 92 out of 120 (76.67%) and the lowest scorer was a Filipino major who landed the score 54 out of 150 (36.00%).

The results of this study conforms with the studies of Antiojo (2017) in Cavite State University-Naic of the Cavite State University and of Guazon and Marpa (2013) in Philippine Normal University which concludes that the Major and Professional Education subjects were the areas in the Licensure Examination for Teachers where graduates find difficult.

Recommendations

Based on the results and discussions, it was evident that the overall mean score in the Licensure Examination for Teachers was passing but generally quite low especially in the Professional Education Subject; hence it is highly recommended that a review for the LET should given highlighting the Professional Education Subject, especially to the Early Childhood Education majors who recorded the only failing mark among all the degrees in all the subjects.

Remedial or Refresher courses that is relevant to the LET can be facilitated in a big group or through a seminar or webinar type program.

A serious retention protocol or a strict measure on who can continue in the Education programs or who are liable to take the LET must be regulated and institutionalized, for instance, a comprehensive examination could be given to the Education students' final year to identify the students who are ready to take the LET and who are not.

Also, the College of Education faculty and administrators must raise the standards and encourage students to do better in the Licensure Examination for Teachers.

The College of Education could also conduct studies considering the integration of the LET competencies and the Department of Education (DepEd) and NCBTS (National Competency-Based Teacher Standards) requirements among the different courses offered in the Education curricula.

Furthermore, a follow-up study that would measure if there is a difference or relationship of any variables/correlates/predictors in the performance in Licensure Examination, such as qualifications of the faculty, methods or strategies of teaching, and other factors that contribute to the students' performance in the Licensure Examination, should be undertaken.

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